

THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN METAPHOR AND SIMILE

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***Annotation:** Although there is a lot of research on metaphor and simile in English linguistics, there is a growing interest in it. Because in order to use words in the language, it is necessary to know not only the meaning of words, but also their figurative meanings. It means that in linguistics there is a need for a comprehensive study of metaphor and simile. In the article we tried to clarify the concepts of metaphor and simile, the key differences between them.*

***Keywords:** semasiology, stylistic devices, metaphor, simile, figures of speech, semantically.*

INTRODUCTION

There are a lot of branches in linguistics. One of them **semasiology** is a branch of linguistics whose area of study is meaning. All stylistic effects are based on the interplay between different kinds of meaning on different levels (grammatical, lexical, logical, denotative, connotative, emotive, evaluative, expressive and stylistic)¹. **Stylistic devices** make your speeches, essays etc. more interesting and lively and help you to get and keep your reader's / listener's attention.

The most popular lexical stylistic devices are *simile, metaphor, synecdoche, metonymy, personification, apostrophe, charactonym, symbol*, alliteration, allusion, anaphora, antithesis, hyperbole, hypophora, litotes, onomatopoeia, parallelism and so on.

Lexical stylistic devices reveal the following patterns:

¹ <https://www.grammarly.com>

- Interplay of different types of lex. meaning;
- Intensification of characteristic traits of the phenomena described;
- Intentional mixing of word of different stylistic aspects.

MAIN PART

According to our theme we pay more attention to metaphor and simile. As mentioned above our task is to clarify the difference of these two two aspects of linguistics. Firstly, **metaphor** is transfer of the name of the object to another object on the basis of similarity, likeness of 2 objects. The word *metaphor* comes from the Greek *metaphorá*, meaning “a transfer.” In essence, the use of *metaphor* involves the transfer of meaning from one thing to another. Metaphor has no formal limitations: it can be a word, a phrase, any part of the sentence or a whole, even a part of the text or a whole text ². A metaphor can exist only within a context. The metaphor brings to the surface, the reader to have a new fresh look at the object³. The chief function is to create images. Stylistic metaphors can be classified ***semantically and structurally***. Metaphor may be based on similarity :

Appearance or form – nut

Temperature – boiling hot

Similarity of color – violet

Similarity of function of use – hand

The names of animals – ass

-The world is your **oyster**.

-His computer was a **dinosaur**. [=his computer was very old]

-The puppy was **the ray of sunshine** the family needed.

-Your eyes are **stars**.

A **simile** is a figure of speech that is mainly used to compare two or more things that possess a similar quality. *Simile* comes from the Latin *similis*, meaning “similar.” A *simile* states that two things are **similar** (and explicitly signals that a

² Talmy, L. (2000). *Toward a cognitive semantics*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press. [[Google Scholar](#)]

³ <https://en.wikipedia.org/>

comparison is being made by using *like* or *as*) It uses words such as ‘like’ or ‘as’ to make the comparison. According to the Oxford Learner’s Dictionary, a simile is defined as “a word or phrase that compares something to something else, using the words *like* or *as*.” The Cambridge Dictionary defines a simile as “an expression comparing one thing with another, always including the words *as* or *like*”⁴. The Merriam-Webster Dictionary defines a simile as “a figure of speech comparing two unlike things that is often introduced by *like* or *as*.” “A simile is an expression which describes a person or thing as being similar to someone or something else”, according to the Collins Dictionary.

-My love is **like a red rose**.

-My brother and I **fight like cats and dogs** all the time.

-Life *is like a box of chocolates*.

-There were rockets **like a flight of scintillating birds singing with sweet voices**.

(J.R.R. Tolkien, *The Fellowship of the Ring*)

A simile is generally used in a sentence to make comparisons between two or more nouns and this is done with the use of words such as ‘like’ or ‘as’. The general idea of using a simile with the word ‘as’ is by using a noun that is known for a particular quality. For example: as proud as a peacock, as busy as a bee and so on. A simile is a direct comparison of two like or unlike things. A simile helps your reader or listener visualise, understand and have a better conception of the quality of the nouns being compared. It makes it a lot more vivid and descriptive. In other words, it can be said that similes can be used to provide a mental image to your reader or listener.

[Metaphor](#) is a much broader term than *simile*. In the broadest sense, the word *metaphor* refers to a symbol that represents something else. So, for example, you could say something like “In the novel, the horse that keeps appearing and disappearing is a metaphor for death.” Many of what we call figures of speech are technically types of *metaphors* (even *similes* can be thought of as a type

⁴ <https://www.britannica.com/dictionary/eb/qa/Similes-and-Metaphors>

of *metaphor*)⁵. In terms of writing and speech, a *metaphor* is the applying of a word or phrase to something that's not literally related in order to suggest a resemblance.

Similes and *metaphors* are two of the most common [figures of speech](#)—expressions that allow us to make comparisons, connections, and descriptions beyond [literal](#) ones. Similes and metaphors are both figures of speech that are used to make a comparison between two things that are not alike⁶.

-A **simile** says that one thing "is like" or "is as ... as" another thing.;

-A **metaphor** says that one thing "is" another thing. Metaphors do not use the words "like" or "as" in their comparisons;

-Though metaphors and similes are meant to make comparisons and show resemblances, they differ on some levels;

-Metaphor is an implied comparison but simile is a direct comparison;

-Metaphor does not use any specific words to make a comparison but simile uses words such a "like" or "as" to make a comparison;

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⁵ Fallah, N., & Moini, M. R. (2016) *Metaphor and the Social World*, 6(1), 79–102.

⁶ <https://www.grammarly.com>

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the difference between simile and metaphor can be drawn clearly on the following grounds:

1. A simile is a figurative statement, wherein two, unlike objects, are compared, by means of words as and like. Conversely, a metaphor is a figure of speech which can be a word or phrase for one thing that points out another, to express that they are similar.
2. A simile is a metaphor, but vice versa is not true, because, a simile is a type of metaphor. As against, a metaphor is a kind of non-literal language.
3. Similes contain a direct comparison of two things, metaphor impliedly compare two objects.
4. In the case of simile, we make use of connectives such as ‘like’ and ‘as’ to indicate that the subject is similar to something. On the other hand, metaphors do not use the connectives as it indicates that the subject is something else .

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